

EXISTENCE AND UNIQUENESS OF THE P-GENERALIZED MODIFIED ERROR FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT. In this article, we define a p-generalized modified error function as the solution to a non-linear ordinary differential equation of second order, with a Robin type boundary condition at $x = 0$. We prove existence and uniqueness of a non-negative C^∞ solution by using a fixed point argument. We show that the p-generalized modified error function converges to the p-modified error function defined as the solution to a similar problem with a Dirichlet boundary condition. In both problems, for $p = 1$, the generalized modified error function and the modified error function are recovered. In addition, we analyze the existence and uniqueness of solution to a problem with a Neumann boundary condition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceratani et al. [5] studied a fusion Stefan problem with variable thermal conductivity and a Robin boundary condition at the fixed face $x = 0$. They studied

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right), \quad 0 < x < s(t), \quad t > 0, \quad (1.1)$$

$$k(T(0, t)) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}(0, t) = \frac{h}{\sqrt{t}} [T(0, t) - T_0], \quad t > 0, \quad (1.2)$$

$$T(s(t), t) = T_f, \quad t > 0, \quad (1.3)$$

$$k(T(s(t), t)) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}(s(t), t) = -\rho l \dot{s}(t), \quad t > 0, \quad (1.4)$$

$$s(0) = 0, \quad (1.5)$$

where the unknown functions are the temperature T and the free boundary s separating both phases. The parameters $\rho > 0$ (density), $l > 0$ (latent heat per unit mass), T_f (phase-change temperature), $T_0 > T_f$ (bulk temperature), $h > 0$ (coefficient that characterizes the heat transfer at $x = 0$), and c (specific heat) are all known constants.

Problem (1.1)–(1.5) is a phase-change problem known in the literature as a Stefan problem. It corresponds to the melting of a semi-infinite material which is initially solid at the phase-change temperature T_f . As $T_0 > T_f$, a phase-change interface

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$x = s(t)$, $t > 0$ is beginning at $t = 0$ with the initial position $s(0) = 0$. Then, the temperature of the liquid phase is $T = T(x, t)$ defined in the domain $0 < x < s(t)$, $t > 0$, and the temperature of the solid phase is $T = 0$ defined in the domain $x > s(t)$, $t > 0$.

In [6], the thermal conductivity k is defined as

$$k(T) = k_0 \left(1 + \delta \left(\frac{T - T_f}{T_0 - T_f} \right) \right), \quad (1.6)$$

where δ is a given positive constant and k_0 is the reference thermal conductivity. The existence of a solution to (1.1)–(1.5) when the thermal conductivity $k(T)$ is defined by (1.6) has been proved through the existence of what the authors in [5] called a *generalized modified error function* (GME), which is defined as the solution to the ordinary differential

$$[(1 + \delta y(x))y'(x)]' + 2xy'(x) = 0, \quad 0 < x < +\infty, \quad (1.7a)$$

$$(1 + \delta y(0))y'(0) - \gamma y(0) = 0, \quad (1.7b)$$

$$y(+\infty) = 1, \quad (1.7c)$$

where

$$\gamma = 2 \text{ Bi}, \quad \text{Bi} = \frac{h\sqrt{\alpha_0}}{k_0} \quad (\text{generalized Biot number}), \quad (1.8)$$

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{k_0}{\rho c} \quad (\text{thermal diffusivity}). \quad (1.9)$$

The solution to (1.1)–(1.5) is given as a function of the solution of (1.7) through the similarity variable $x/(2\sqrt{\alpha_0 t})$, see [5, 6, 12]. More explanations are given in [1, 9, 14].

Motivated by [10] we define a generalized thermal conductivity as

$$k(T) = k_0 \left(1 + \delta \left(\frac{T - T_f}{T_0 - T_f} \right)^p \right), \quad p \geq 1. \quad (1.10)$$

Then the existence of a solution to (1.1)–(1.5) with k given by (1.10) will be studied through the *p-generalized modified error function* (p-GME) which we define as the solution to the nonlinear differential problem

$$[(1 + \delta y^p(x))y'(x)]' + 2xy'(x) = 0, \quad 0 < x < +\infty, \quad (1.11a)$$

$$(1 + \delta y^p(0))y'(0) - \gamma y(0) = 0, \quad (1.11b)$$

$$y(+\infty) = 1. \quad (1.11c)$$

Note that when $p = 1$, we recover the problem studied in [4, 5] and originally defined in [6, 12]. Others studies for $p = 1$ can be found in [2, 13]. In that sense, the p-GME function constitutes a mathematical generalization of the GME function.

With the purpose of proving existence and uniqueness of the p-GME function, i.e. a solution to (1.11), we define a convenient contracting mapping, in Section 2. In Section 3, we study the asymptotic behavior of the p-GME function when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$. We will show that this function converges to the solution of an ordinary differential equation that arises by changing the Robin condition at $x = 0$ [3] by a Dirichlet condition. Finally, in Section 4 we change the Robin condition by a Neumann condition in a solidification process and analyze the existence and uniqueness of a new ordinary differential problem. In conclusion, the aim of this paper is to prove existence and uniqueness of a solution to three ordinary differential problems that

have been motivated by Stefan problems. This is done imposing different boundary conditions at the fixed face $x = 0$: Robin, Dirichlet and Neumann conditions.

2. EXISTENCE AND UNIQUENESS OF THE P-GME FUNCTION

Let us define

$$X = \{h : \mathbb{R}_0^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : h \text{ is a bounded and continuous real-valued function}\}, \quad (2.1)$$

$$K = \{h \in X : \|h\|_\infty \leq 1, 0 \leq h, h(+\infty) = 1\}. \quad (2.2)$$

We remark that K is a non-empty closed convex and bounded subset of the Banach space X with the norm

$$\|h\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}_0^+} |h(x)| < \infty;$$

see [7, page 2487], [8, page 152], [11, page 132].

In this section we prove existence and uniqueness of the p-GME function (problem (1.11)) by using the Banach fixed point theorem. First, we show that the ordinary differential problem (1.11) becomes equivalent to an integral equation. We consider that γ is a parameter for problem (1.11), and in Section 3 we will study the asymptotic behavior when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$.

Theorem 2.1. *Let $\delta \geq 0$, $\gamma > 0$, $p \geq 1$. For each $\gamma > 0$, the function $y_\gamma \in K$ is a solution to problem (1.11) if and only if y_γ is a fixed point to the operator $T_\gamma : K \rightarrow K$ given by*

$$T_\gamma(h)(x) = \frac{1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_h(\eta) d\eta}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_h(\eta) d\eta}, \quad x \geq 0, \quad (2.3)$$

with

$$f_h(x) = \frac{1}{\Psi_h(x)} \exp\left(-2 \int_0^x \frac{\xi}{\Psi_h(\xi)} d\xi\right), \quad \Psi_h(x) = 1 + \delta h^p(x). \quad (2.4)$$

Proof. Notice first that for each $y = y_\gamma \in K$ we can easily obtain

$$\frac{\exp(-\eta^2)}{1 + \delta} \leq f_y(\eta) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{\eta^2}{1 + \delta}\right), \quad (2.5)$$

from where it follows that

$$0 < \frac{\gamma\sqrt{\pi}}{2(1 + \delta)} < 1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_y(\eta) d\eta \leq 1 + \frac{\gamma\sqrt{1 + \delta}\sqrt{\pi}}{2}. \quad (2.6)$$

Taking into account (2.6), $T_\gamma(y)$ is a continuous function, since $y \in X$. Also, according to (2.1)–(2.3) and (2.6), $T_\gamma(y) \in K$.

Through the substitution $v = y'$, the ordinary differential equation (1.7a) is equivalent to

$$-\frac{\Psi'_y(x) + 2x}{\Psi_y(x)} = \frac{v'(x)}{v(x)},$$

from where we obtain

$$y(x) = y(0) + c_0 \int_0^x f_y(\eta) d\eta.$$

Then, condition (1.7b) is satisfied if and only if $c_0 = \gamma y(0)$. In addition, from (1.7c) we obtain

$$y(0) = \left(1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_y(\eta) d\eta\right)^{-1}. \quad (2.7)$$

Therefore, y is a solution to problem (1.11) if and only if y is a fixed point of the operator T_γ , i.e. $y(x) = T_\gamma(y)(x)$ for all $x \geq 0$. Conversely, if y is a fixed point of the operator T_γ we obtain immediately that (1.7c) is verified, and $y(0)$ is given by (2.7). Then, by differentiation (1.7a) and (1.7b) hold, and then y is a solution of (1.11). \square

Remark 2.2. The notation y_γ, T_γ is adopted to emphasize the dependence of the solution to (1.11) on γ , although it also depends on p and δ . This fact is going to facilitate the subsequent analysis of the asymptotic behavior of y_γ when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, to be presented in Section 3.

By Theorem 2.1, we will focus on proving that T_γ is a contracting mapping on K . For that purpose, we need the following lemmas.

Lemma 2.3. *Let $y_1, y_2 \in K$, $\delta \geq 0, \gamma > 0, p \geq 1$ and $x \geq 0$. Then, the following estimates hold:*

$$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2(1+\delta)} \leq \left| \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta \right| \leq \sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}, \quad (2.8)$$

$$\left| \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_1}(\eta)} - \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_2}(\eta)} \right| \leq \delta p \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty, \quad (2.9)$$

$$\left| \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_1}(\xi)} d\xi\right) - \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} d\xi\right) \right| \leq \frac{2\delta p \eta^2}{\exp\left(\frac{\eta^2}{1+\delta}\right)} \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty, \quad (2.10)$$

$$\int_0^x |f_{y_1}(\eta) - f_{y_2}(\eta)| d\eta \leq \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \delta p \sqrt{1+\delta} (2+\delta) \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty, \quad (2.11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{1+\gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{1}{1+\gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{2(1+\delta)^{5/2}}{\gamma \sqrt{\pi}} \delta p (2+\delta) \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Proof. We follow the method was developed in [4].

Inequality (2.8) follows from integrating (2.5) in $(0, +\infty)$. For inequality (2.9) we note that from the Mean Value Theorem applied to the function $r(x) = x^p$ and the fact that $1 \leq \Psi_y(x) \leq 1 + \delta$ for all $y \in K$, we obtain

$$\left| \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_1}(\eta)} - \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_2}(\eta)} \right| \leq \delta |y_2^p(\eta) - y_1^p(\eta)| \leq \delta p \|y_2 - y_1\|_\infty.$$

For inequality (2.10), applying the Mean Value Theorem to $r(x) = \exp(-2x)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_1}(\xi)} d\xi\right) - \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} d\xi\right) \right| \\ & \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\eta^2}{1+\delta}\right) \int_0^\eta \left| \frac{\xi}{\Psi_{y_1}(\xi)} - \frac{\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} \right| d\xi \\ & \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\eta^2}{1+\delta}\right) \eta \int_0^\eta \left| \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_1}(\xi)} - \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} \right| d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account (2.9) we obtain the corresponding estimate. For inequality (2.11), from items (2.9) and (2.10) we obtain

$$\int_0^x |f_{y_1}(\eta) - f_{y_2}(\eta)| d\eta$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \int_0^x \left\{ \left| f_{y_1}(\eta) - \frac{\exp(-2 \int_0^x \frac{\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} d\xi)}{\Psi_{y_1}(\eta)} \right| + \left| \frac{\exp(-2 \int_0^x \frac{\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} d\xi)}{\Psi_{y_1}(\eta)} - f_{y_2}(\eta) \right| \right\} d\eta \\
&\leq \int_0^x \left\{ \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_1}(\eta)} \left| \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_1}(\xi)} d\xi\right) - \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} d\xi\right) \right| \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \exp\left(\int_0^\eta \frac{-2\xi}{\Psi_{y_2}(\xi)} d\xi\right) \left| \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_1}(\eta)} - \frac{1}{\Psi_{y_2}(\eta)} \right| \right\} d\eta \\
&\leq \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty \delta p \int_0^x \exp\left(\frac{-\eta^2}{1+\delta}\right) (2\eta^2 + 1) d\eta \\
&= \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty \delta p \sqrt{1+\delta} \left[\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} (2+\delta) \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{1+\delta}}\right) - x \sqrt{1+\delta} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2}{1+\delta}\right) \right] \\
&\leq \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \delta p \sqrt{1+\delta} (2+\delta) \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty.
\end{aligned}$$

Inequality (2.12) follows immediately by using (2.6) and (2.11). \square

Lemma 2.4. *Let $\gamma > 0$, $p \geq 1$ and*

$$g_\gamma(x) = xp(1+x)^{3/2} \left[(2+x)(1+(1+x)^{3/2}) + \frac{2}{\gamma\sqrt{\pi}}(1+x) \right], \quad x \geq 0.$$

Then there exist a unique $\delta_\gamma > 0$ such that $g_\gamma(\delta_\gamma) = 1$.

The above lemma follows immediately from the fact that g_γ is an increasing function, $g_\gamma(0) = 0$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} g_\gamma(x) = +\infty$. Now, we are able to formulate the following result.

Theorem 2.5. *Let $\gamma > 0$ and $p \geq 1$. The problem (1.11) has a unique solution $y_\gamma \in K$ if and only if $0 \leq \delta < \delta_\gamma$, where δ_γ is given by Lemma 2.4. Moreover, y_γ is a C^∞ function in \mathbb{R}^+ with the following properties:*

$$y'_\gamma(x) > 0, \quad y''_\gamma(x) < 0, \quad \forall x \geq 0. \quad (2.13)$$

Proof. Let $y_1, y_2 \in K$ and $x \geq 0$. Taking into account Lemma 2.3, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&|T_\gamma(y_1)(x) - T_\gamma(y_2)(x)| \\
&\leq \left| \frac{1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \\
&\quad + \left| \frac{1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \\
&\leq \frac{\gamma \int_0^x |f_{y_1}(\eta) - f_{y_2}(\eta)| d\eta}{\left| 1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta \right|} \\
&\quad + \left| 1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta \right| \left| \frac{1}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_1}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{1}{1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_2}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \\
&\leq g_\gamma(\delta) \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty.
\end{aligned}$$

Then from Lemma 2.4, if $0 \leq \delta < \delta_\gamma$ it follows that T_γ is a contracting mapping what allows to apply the Banach fixed point theorem. Therefore, the problem (1.11) has a unique non-negative continuous solution. Moreover, by differentiation and easy computation the solution is a C^∞ function in \mathbb{R}^+ with the useful properties (2.13). \square

3. ASYMPTOTIC BEHAVIOR OF P-GME FUNCTION WHEN $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$

In this section if we consider the Stefan problem (1.1)–(1.5) and we change the Robin condition (1.2) by a Dirichlet condition.

$$T(0, t) = T_0 > 0, \quad (3.1)$$

we obtain the ordinary differential problem

$$[(1 + \delta y^p(x))y'(x)]' + 2xy'(x) = 0, \quad 0 < x < +\infty, \quad (3.2a)$$

$$y(0) = 0, \quad (3.2b)$$

$$y(+\infty) = 1. \quad (3.2c)$$

For the special case $p = 1$, the solution to this problem is called *modified error function* (ME) and was considered in [2, 4, 5, 6, 12]. In [4] the existence and uniqueness of the ME function was proved. Moreover, if it is considered $\delta = 0$, the classical error function defined by

$$\operatorname{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x \exp(-z^2) dz, \quad x > 0, \quad (3.3)$$

arises as a solution.

In a similar way to the above section we can analyze the existence and uniqueness of the *p-modified error function* (p-ME), which is defined as the solution to problem (3.2) and constitutes a generalization of the ME function.

Now, let us define

$$K^* = \{h \in X : \|h\|_\infty \leq 1, 0 \leq h, h(0) = 0, h(+\infty) = 1\},$$

where X is given by (2.1). We remark that K^* is a non-empty closed convex and bounded subset of the Banach space X . We will show that the ordinary differential problem (3.2) becomes equivalent to an integral equation.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $\delta \geq 0$, $p \geq 1$. Then the function $y^* \in K^*$ is a solution to (3.2) if and only if y^* is a fixed point of the operator $T^* : K^* \rightarrow K^*$ given by:*

$$T^*(h)(x) = \frac{\int_0^x f_h(\eta) d\eta}{\int_0^\infty f_h(\eta) d\eta}, \quad x \geq 0, \quad (3.4)$$

with f_h defined by (2.4).

Proof. In a similar way as in the proof of Theorem 2.1, the operator T^* is well defined and it is easy to see that

$$y^*(x) = y^*(0) + c_0^* \int_0^x f_y^*(\eta) d\eta,$$

with $y^*(0) = 0$ and $c_0^* = (\int_0^\infty f_h(\eta) d\eta)^{-1}$. Then, using (3.2b) and (3.2c), we obtain (3.4). Therefore, y^* is a solution to (3.2) if and only if y^* is a fixed point of the operator T^* . \square

To prove that the operator T^* is a contracting mapping on K^* , we enunciate the following lemmas which proofs are analogous to Lemma 2.3 and Lemma 2.4.

Lemma 3.2. *Let $y_1^*, y_2^* \in K^*$, $\delta \geq 0$, $p \geq 1$ and $x \geq 0$. Then*

$$\left| \frac{1}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_1^*}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{1}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \leq \frac{2(1 + \delta)^{5/2}}{\sqrt{\pi}} \delta p(2 + \delta) \|y_1^* - y_2^*\|_\infty.$$

Lemma 3.3. Let $p \geq 1$ and

$$g^*(x) = xp(1+x)^{3/2}(2+x)(1+(1+x)^{3/2}), \quad x \geq 0.$$

Then there exists a unique $\delta^* > 0$ such that $g^*(\delta^*) = 1$.

Theorem 3.4. Problem (3.2) has a unique solution $y^* \in K$ if and only if $0 \leq \delta < \delta^*$, where δ^* is given by Lemma 3.3. Moreover, y^* is a C^∞ function in \mathbb{R}^+ .

Proof. Let $y_1^*, y_2^* \in K^*$ and $x \geq 0$. Taking into account Lemmas 2.3 and 3.2 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & |T^*(y_1^*)(x) - T^*(y_2^*)(x)| \\ & \leq \left| \frac{\int_0^x f_{y_1^*}(\eta) d\eta}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_1^*}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{\int_0^x f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta} \right| + \left| \frac{\int_0^x f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_1^*}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{\int_0^x f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\int_0^x |f_{y_1^*}(\eta) - f_{y_2^*}(\eta)| d\eta}{\left| \int_0^\infty f_{y_1^*}(\eta) d\eta \right|} + \left| \int_0^x f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta \right| \left| \frac{1}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_1^*}(\eta) d\eta} - \frac{1}{\int_0^\infty f_{y_2^*}(\eta) d\eta} \right| \\ & \leq g^*(\delta^*) \|y_1^* - y_2^*\|_\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Then from Lemma 3.3, if $0 \leq \delta < \delta^*$ it follows that T^* is a contracting mapping what allows to apply the Banach fixed point theorem. Therefore, the problem (3.2) has a unique non-negative continuous solution which is also a C^∞ function by simple differentiation in \mathbb{R}^+ . \square

To problem (1.11), we impose a Robin boundary condition characterized by the coefficient $\gamma > 0$ at $x = 0$. This condition constitutes a generalization of the Dirichlet condition, in the sense that taking the limit when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$ in condition (1.7b), we obtain condition (3.2b). Now, we show that the solution to problem (1.11) converges to the solution to problem (3.2) when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$. For this purpose, first, we need the following lemmas which proofs are immediate.

Lemma 3.5. For every $p \geq 1$, when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, the following convergence results hold

- (a) $T_\gamma(h)(x) \rightarrow T^*(h)(x)$ for every $h \in K$ and $x \geq 0$.
- (b) $g_\gamma(x) \rightarrow g^*(x)$ for every $x \geq 0$.
- (c) $\delta_\gamma \rightarrow \delta^*$.

In addition $g_\gamma(x) \geq g^*(x)$ and $\delta_\gamma < \delta^*$ for all $x \geq 0, \gamma > 0$.

Lemma 3.6. Let $p \geq 1$ and

$$C(x) = 2xp(1+x)^3(2+x), \quad x \geq 0. \quad (3.5)$$

Then there exists a unique $\hat{\delta} > 0$ such that $C(\hat{\delta}) = 1$.

Theorem 3.7. Let $p \geq 1$ and $0 \leq \delta < \min\{\hat{\delta}, \delta_\gamma\}$. Then $\|y_\gamma - y^*\|_\infty \rightarrow 0$ when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$. Furthermore, the order of convergence is $1/\gamma$ when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. First let us note that if $0 \leq \delta < \min\{\hat{\delta}, \delta_\gamma\}$, then as $\delta_\gamma < \delta^*$, we obtain that y_γ and y^* are well defined because of Theorems 2.5 and 3.4. Then for $x \geq 0$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |y_\gamma(x) - y^*(x)| \\ & = \left| \frac{(1 + \gamma \int_0^x f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta) (\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta) - (\int_0^x f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta) (1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta)}{(1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta) (\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta)} \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \left| \left[\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta + \gamma \left(\int_0^x f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) - \int_0^x f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - \gamma \left(\int_0^x f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right] / \left[\left(1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right] \right| \\
&= \left| \left[\int_x^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta + \gamma \left(\int_0^x f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - \gamma \left(\int_0^x f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right] / \left[\left(1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right] \right| \\
&\leq \left| \left[\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta + \gamma \left(\int_0^x f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) - \int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \gamma \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta - \int_0^x f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. \div \left[\left(1 + \gamma \int_0^\infty f_{y_\gamma}(\eta) d\eta \right) \left(\int_0^\infty f_{y^*}(\eta) d\eta \right) \right] \right| \\
&\leq \left[\sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} + \gamma \sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \left(\int_0^\infty |f_{y^*}(\eta) - f_{y_\gamma}(\eta)| d\eta \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \gamma \sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \left(\int_0^x |f_{y^*}(\eta) - f_{y_\gamma}(\eta)| d\eta \right) \right] / \left[\frac{\gamma \sqrt{\pi}}{2(1+\delta)} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2(1+\delta)} \right] \\
&\leq \frac{\sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} + 2\gamma \sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \int_0^\infty |f_{y^*}(\eta) - f_{y_\gamma}(\eta)| d\eta}{\frac{\gamma \pi}{4(1+\delta)^2}} \\
&\leq \frac{4(1+\delta)^2}{\gamma \pi} \left(\sqrt{1+\delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} + \gamma \frac{\pi}{4} \delta p(1+\delta)(2+\delta) \|y_\gamma - y^*\|_\infty \right) \\
&\leq \frac{2(1+\delta)^{5/2}}{\gamma \pi} + 2(1+\delta)^3 \delta p(2+\delta) \|y_\gamma - y^*\|_\infty.
\end{aligned}$$

The above inequalities are obtained by applying Lemma 2.3, and they lead to

$$(1 - C(\delta)) \|y_\gamma - y^*\|_\infty \leq \frac{1}{\gamma} \left(\frac{2(1+\delta)^{5/2}}{\sqrt{\pi}} \right),$$

with C defined by (3.5). Finally, the desired convergence and order of convergence in Theorem 3.7 are obtained by noting that if $0 \leq \delta < \hat{\delta}$, then $0 \leq C(\delta) < 1$ because of Lemma 3.6. \square

4. EXISTENCE AND UNIQUENESS CONSIDERING A NEUMANN CONDITION

In this section we consider a solidification Stefan problem with a Neumann condition at the fixed face $x = 0$, given by

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right), \quad 0 < x < s(t), \quad t > 0, \quad (4.1)$$

$$k(T(0, t)) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}(0, t) = \frac{q_0}{\sqrt{t}}, \quad t > 0, \quad (4.2)$$

$$T(s(t), t) = T_f, \quad t > 0, \quad (4.3)$$

$$k(T(s(t), t)) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}(s(t), t) = \rho l \dot{s}(t), \quad t > 0, \quad (4.4)$$

$$s(0) = 0, \quad (4.5)$$

where the unknown functions are the temperature T and the free boundary s separating both phases. The parameters $\rho > 0$ (density), $l > 0$ (latent heat per unit mass), T_f (phase-change temperature), $q_0 > 0$ (characterizes the heat flux on the fixed face $x = 0$ of the face-change material which can be determined experimentally) and $c > 0$ (specific heat) are all known constants. In this case, the thermal conductivity k is defined as

$$k(T) = k_0 \left(1 + \delta \left(\frac{T}{T_f} \right)^p \right), \quad p \geq 1, \quad (4.6)$$

where δ is a given positive constant and k_0 is the reference thermal conductivity.

In a similar way as in previous sections, this Stefan problem leads us to the study the ordinary differential problem

$$[(1 + \delta y^p(x))y'(x)]' + 2xy'(x) = 0, \quad 0 < x < +\infty, \quad (4.7a)$$

$$(1 + \delta y^p(0))y'(0) = \gamma^*, \quad (4.7b)$$

$$y(+\infty) = 1, \quad (4.7c)$$

where

$$\gamma^* = 2 \text{Bi}^* \quad \text{with} \quad \text{Bi}^* = \frac{q_0 \sqrt{\alpha_0}}{k_0 T_f}. \quad (4.8)$$

In a similar way to the above sections we can state the following results:

Theorem 4.1. *Let $\delta \geq 0$, $p \geq 1$ and $0 < \gamma^* \leq \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi(1+\delta)}}$. Then $y_{\gamma^*} \in K$ is a solution to (4.7) if and only if y_{γ^*} is a fixed point of the operator $T_{\gamma^*} : K \rightarrow K$ given by*

$$T_{\gamma^*}(h)(x) = 1 - \gamma^* \int_x^{+\infty} f_h(\eta) d\eta, \quad x \geq 0, \quad (4.9)$$

with f_h defined by (2.4) and K given by (2.2).

Proof. Given $y_{\gamma^*} \in K$ and taking into account (2.5), we obtain

$$0 < \frac{\gamma^* \text{erfc}(x)}{1 + \delta} \leq \gamma^* \int_x^\infty f_y(\eta) d\eta < \frac{\gamma^* \sqrt{1 + \delta} \sqrt{\pi}}{2} \leq 1. \quad (4.10)$$

Note that from (4.9) we have that $T_{\gamma^*}(y_{\gamma^*})$ is an analytic function, since $y_{\gamma^*} \in X$. Also, according to (4.9) and (4.10), $T_{\gamma^*}(y_{\gamma^*}) \in K$.

In a similar way as in the proof of Theorem 2.1, y_{γ^*} is a solution to (4.7) if and only if y_{γ^*} is a fixed point of the operator T_{γ^*} . \square

Theorem 4.2. *Let $p \geq 1$, $\delta > 0$ and $0 < \gamma^* \leq \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi(1+\delta)}}$. Then (4.7) has a unique C^∞ solution $y_{\gamma^*} \in K$ if and only if $\delta < \delta_{\gamma^*}$ where δ_{γ^*} is the unique solution to the equation $g(x) = 1$, with*

$$g(x) = x \frac{p}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left[(1+x) \left(\sqrt{1+x} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{4}\right) + \sqrt{\pi} \right) + \sqrt{\pi} \right].$$

Proof. Let $y_{1_{\gamma^*}}, y_{2_{\gamma^*}} \in K$ and $x \geq 0$. Taking into account (2.9) and (2.10) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & |T_{\gamma^*}(y_{1_{\gamma^*}})(x) - T_{\gamma^*}(y_{2_{\gamma^*}})(x)| \\ & \leq \|y_1 - y_2\|_\infty \delta p \gamma^* \left[(1 + \delta)^{3/2} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{1 + \delta}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{1 + \delta}\right) + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \right) + \sqrt{1 + \delta} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \delta \frac{p}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left[(1 + \delta) \left(\sqrt{1 + \delta} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{4}\right) + \sqrt{\pi} \right) + \sqrt{\pi} \right] \|y_{1,\gamma^*} - y_{2,\gamma^*}\|_{\infty} \\ &\leq g(\delta) \|y_{1,\gamma^*} - y_{2,\gamma^*}\|_{\infty}. \end{aligned}$$

Since g is an increasing function such that $g(0) = 0$ and $g(+\infty) = +\infty$, there exists a unique $\delta_{\gamma^*} > 0$ with $g(\delta_{\gamma^*}) = 1$.

Then, if $0 \leq \delta < \delta_{\gamma^*}$ it follows that T_{γ^*} is a contracting mapping what allows to apply the Banach fixed point theorem. Therefore, the problem (4.7) has a unique non-negative continuous solution which is also a C^{∞} function. \square

Conclusion. In this article, the ordinary differential problems studied in [4, 5] have been generalized by defining what we call the p-GME function and the p-ME function corresponding to the case when a Robin or Dirichlet boundary condition are imposed at $x = 0$, respectively. In both problems, existence and uniqueness of C^{∞} solution has been proved by defining convenient contracting mappings. In addition it has been studied the behavior of the p-GME function when the coefficient γ that characterizes the Robin condition goes to infinity, obtaining its convergence to the p-ME function with an order of convergence of the type $1/\gamma$ when $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$. Finally, existence and uniqueness of a solution to a solidification problem with a Neumann condition has been studied.

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